
THE ROLE OF AUDIT QUALITY IN ENHANCING THE PERFORMANCE OF BANKS IN NIGERIA

Chiamaka Grace Eze

Department of Banking and Finance, Osun State Polytechnic, Iree, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Audit quality has been reported to support the efficient functioning of capital markets since it instills confidence of stakeholders in the credibility and integrity of corporate financial reports. Therefore, this study attempts to examine the impact of audit quality on the performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria using both accounting and market measures of assessing performance. We employed 9 sampled banks out of 16 listed on Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) market for a period of eight financial years between 2012 and 2019 based on panel data approach. Furthermore, data were sourced from the annual reports and financial statements of the sampled banks. This study employs correlation multiple regression techniques to analyse the observed variables in the model. The results revealed that both audit fee and auditor size show a positive and significant relationship with accounting measure of bank's performance (ROA). Conversely, the audit fees and size have positive but not significant effect on market measure of performance, Tobin's Q. The study therefore, recommends that the executives should engage the services provided by audit firms whose integrity and character is unquestionable in order to improve the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.</p>	<p>Audit Quality, Financial Performance, Market performance, listed banks.</p>

1. Introduction

Auditing is a monitoring device that is required for restoring sanity in financial reports prepared by directors which in most cases are perceived to contain fraud, errors or other irregularities. This is because high quality audit is expected to remove misstatements contained in financial statements and thus protect the interests of the owners. Stakeholders (creditors, potential investors, shareholders, and others) require financial information that is credible to make informed decisions. Fraudulent financial reports emanate because of information asymmetry occasioned by agency problem between shareholders (owners) and managers (agents). It has been found that performance of organizations that engage in fraud usually deteriorate (Xin, Zhou & Hu 2018) while lack of audit quality usually result in corporate and financial scandals (Soltani, 2014). As a result, audit of financial statements is a critical aspect of the governance of public entities (Sattar, Javeed & Latief (2020).

Audit quality has been reported to support the efficient functioning of capital markets since it instills confidence of stakeholders in the credibility and integrity of corporate financial reports (Monametsi & Agasha (2020). Tyokoso, U-ungwa & Ojonimi (2017) posit that audit quality reduces risk of misstatements in financial reports thereby increasing confidence of investors in the report. Morteza (2014) reports the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision as saying that audit quality is important for efficient prudential supervision of banks while the Financial Stability Board was also reported to have maintained the position that external audits support confidence of investors in capital markets and at the same time contributes to its stability. It has been alluded that reliability of financial statements aids the financial performance of corporate organizations (Iliemena & Okolocha (2019)) resulting in increased investment flows into the organization thus boosting performance.

However, the reliability of the financial report is a function of the quality of the audit exercise performed (Iliemena & Okolocha (2019)). According to IAASB (2011) factors that influence audit quality are input, output and context. Input factors are concerned with things like auditing standards, auditor attributes and audit process. Output factors include the report issued by the auditor as well as communications by the auditor with those charged with governance. Context factors are influences of corporate governance on the conduct of the audit, applicable law and regulations as well as financial reporting framework that promotes robust and transparent disclosure (IAASB, 2011)).

On the other hand, Hu (2015) and Monametsi and Agasha (2020) identified audit failures and financial statement restatements as measurements of the output drivers; fees paid to the audit firm was seen as a measure of the context driver while audit firm size can represent all the three drivers. Other measures of audit quality found in the literature include independence of the audit firm, auditor tenure, auditor rotation and audit firm specialization. A review of the literature showed that considerable research work has been carried out on audit quality and firm performance both in developed and developing countries. The researches have been carried out on industrial and financial firms either individually or in combination and measures of firm performance used vary between market and accounting measures of performance or a combination of the two measures.

For instance, Santos, Cerqueira, & Brandão (2015) used both accounting and market measures to assess performance of both industrial and financial firms in the US. Sayyar, Basiruddin, Rasid & Elhabib (2015) did the same in Malaysia as well as Monametsi & Agasha (2020) in Botswana and Uganda. Eshitemi & Omwenga (2016) and Elewa & El-Haddad (2019) used accounting measure on non-financial firms in Kenya and Egypt respectively just as Chinedu, Nwoha & Udeh, (2019), Iliemena & Okolocha (2019) including Ugwu, Aikpitanyi & Idemudia, (2020) did on listed industrial and manufacturing companies including oil and gas firms in Nigeria. Other Nigerian researchers like Okolie & Izedonmi (2014) and Ugwunta, Ugwuanyi & Ngwa, (2018) were found to have used market measure of performance on listed Nigerian firms.

Literature search also revealed that most of the empirical studies on Nigeria in the area of audit quality and firm performance either studied both industrial and financial firms together or exclude financial firms. Recent studies by Egbunike & Abiahu, (2017), Tyokoso, U-ungwa & Ojonimi (2017) and Ogbodo & Akabuogu, (2018) were found to have been carried out on audit quality and performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. However, while Egbunike and Abiahu, (2017) and Ogbodo & Akabuogu, (2018) used the accounting measure of performance, Tyokoso, U-ungwa & Ojonimi (2017) used Tobin's Q which is a market method of performance. As a result, no study was found in the literature to have used both the accounting and market measures to assess

the performance of Nigerian banks. This study therefore tries to extend the frontiers of knowledge by using both the accounting and market measures to assess the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

1.1 Aim and objectives

This study attempts to examine the impact of audit quality on the performance of DMBs in Nigeria using both accounting and market measures of assessing performance. The study therefore, seeks to provide answers to the following research questions in order to realize the objectives of this paper:

- i. What effect does audit quality has on return on asset (ROA) of DMBs in Nigeria.
- ii. How does audit quality affect the market value

(Tobin's Q) of Nigeria's DMBs.

1.2 Hypotheses

In this study, audit quality is proxied by audit fees and audit firm size. As such the following hypotheses were developed to answer the research questions: **H₀₁**: Audit fees do not have any significant effect on ROA of Nigeria's DMBs.

H₀₂: Auditor size does not significantly affect ROA of Nigeria's DMBs.

H₀₃: Audit fees do not have any significant effect on Tobin's Q of Nigeria's DMBs.

H₀₄: Auditor size does not significantly affect Tobin's Q of Nigeria's DMBs.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

Audit Quality

As a concept, it is believed that audit quality is complex and multi-faceted and as such it does not have a universally accepted definition; rather the term can be subjected to a variety of influences which may be direct and/or indirect (IAASB, 2011). However, audit quality is seen by De Angelo (1981) as "the market-assessed joint probability that a given auditor will both (a) discover a breach in the client's accounting system and (b) report the breach". From the point of view of the users of financial statements, audit quality may mean an audit that ensures that the financial statements do not contain any material misstatement. As a result, earlier scholars like Palmrose (1988) and Teoh & Wong, (1993) perceive audit quality as an act that involves the auditor discovering and reporting a misstatement in financial statements and the two acts being functions of auditors' independence and competency. In this study, audit quality is measured by audit fees and audit firm size.

Audit Fees

Fees represent monetary compensation received by the auditor for services provided to clients. Fees charged by auditors are usually based on efforts exerted by them on the engagement including the level of risk inherent in the assignment (Huyghe, 2017). It is believed that high audit fees denote high quality audit (Colbert and Murray, 1998).

Firm Size

Audit firms are classified as either big or small in accordance with certain parameters which include fee income, number of partners and staff, client base, etc. Big audit firms include Deloitte, KPMG, Price Waterhouse Coopers and Ernst and Young. Large size auditors' big pockets and reputational concerns are seen as justifications for the high fees demanded by them (De Angelo 1981; Okolie & Izedonmi, 2014).

Audit Committee Independence

This is a committee that is statutorily created by the board and it can be useful in guaranteeing the quality of the audit performed (Sattar, Javeed. & Latief, 2020). It is saddled with the responsibility of scrutinizing the financial reports of organization with a view to certifying them. Corporate governance code requires that audit committee be independent and as such, audit committee should be composed of independent executive and nonexecutive directors (Miko & Kamardin, 2014). Talat & Mian (2014) found audit committee independence to be insignificantly related to firm value in Pakistan.

Firm Performance

Demsetz and Lehn (1985) posit that firm performance is the aggregation of the policies and operations of an organization in financial terms by using any of the measures of performance. Thus, Ivungu, Anande. and Ogirah, (2019), identified two broad ways of measuring performance which include accounting and market measures of performance. The accounting measure of performance include return on asset, return on equity, return on investment, etc. Return on assets (ROA) is the most widely used accounting measure of firm performance. Compared to other accounting based methods of performance, it is believed that ROA is a better measure of performance (Shen, et al. 2016; Hutchinson & Gul, 2004). Market measure of performance on the other hand relate to using market value of the shares of a company to evaluate its performance. Market value depicts the value investors placed on a firm's shares in the stock market (Ugwunta, Ugwuanyi & Ngwa, 2018) and this value is a reflection of the fundamentals of the firm among which is audit quality.

Significant numbers of research work have been carried out on audit quality and performance of firms and a good number of these studies confirmed that audit quality actually enhances performance. Hassan and Farouk (2014) posit that the relationship between audit quality and financial performance is positive and significant. Similar findings were obtained by Asghar and Azizi (2010) who noted that big size audit firms with long term relationship with the client is able to constrain management's discretion for accounts manipulations which results in high quality financial statements and consequently higher financial performance for the firm. Also, Iliemena & Okolocha (2019) believe that when the performance of the organization is not so impressive and the auditor performs quality audit, the right information is conveyed to the shareholders through the financial reports and this makes them take steps to remedy the situation. However, Monametsi and Agasha (2020) differ by saying that audit quality should not be relied upon as a measure of performance of organizations since it is not a good measure of governing public companies.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This study is anchored on Agency theory in order to establish the relationship between audit quality and performance of DMBs. Agency theory is created where the principal appoints an agent that is saddled with overseeing the economic resources of the principal. According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), the agents unfortunately have more information about the organization than the principal and this information asymmetry makes the principals to be uncertain whether the agents are actually protecting their interests. Jensen and Meckling (1976) posit that agents may be tempted to be disloyal to their principals whereby they prefer selfinterest over the interest of the principal thereby creating moral hazard. The principals, in order to protect their own interests, put in place a monitoring process like auditing to ensure accountability. Thus, auditing is a control tool that is used by the principal for the purpose of obtaining assurance regarding the reliability of the information contained in the stewardship report prepared by the agent. Since trust is lacking in the principal-agent relationship and the mechanism of audit was put in place to ensure that this trust is not fully eroded, agency theory is therefore relevant

in explaining audit quality and it is thereby adopted in this study. Furthermore, high quality audit is one that ensures that financial information supplied by the organization is free from material misstatement thus eliminating information asymmetry caused by principal-agent conflict in agency theory. Proxies of audit quality used in this study (i. e. audit fees and auditor size) are believed to be capable of ensuring financial information supplied are credible enough to fairly assess the performance of the entity. As a result the a priori expectation is that the variables will exhibit positive relationship with financial performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

Results from empirical studies on audit quality and financial performance of firms are mixed either for market measure of performance or accounting measure. For example, Santos, Cerqueira, and Brandão (2015) used data from US firms to examine the effect of fees for audit and non-audit services on performance. The study used both financial and market measures of performance and results showed significant negative relationships between both measures of performance and proxies of audit quality. A similar study carried out by Sayyar, Basiruddin, Rasid and Elhabib (2015) used ROA &

Tobin's Q to assess performance in Malaysia and found insignificant relationship between audit fees and audit firm rotation on performance, though audit fees was found to be significantly and positively related to market measure of performance.

Using panel data collected from financial reports of nonfinancial firms listed on the Egyptian stock market, Elewa & El-Haddad (2019) found that audit quality (proxied by Big4 and auditor rotation) did not significantly impact return on asset and return on equity. Meanwhile,

Monametsi & Agasha (2020) used ROA and Tobin's Q to measure performance of firms in Uganda and Botswana and result of the study showed that audit fees failed to predict firm performance for the two measures. While Okolie and Izedonmi (2014) used audit firm size to assess market measure of performance of Nigeria's listed firms and found that audit firm size, tenure and client importance significantly influenced market price of shares of listed companies, Hassan & Farouk (2014) as well as Ado, Rashid, Mustapha, & Ademola (2020) confirmed that firm size significantly influence performance but found that audit fees displayed an insignificant relationship with ROA used as a measure of performance for listed firms in Nigeria. Similarly, Ugwunta, Ugwuanyi & Ngwa, (2018) in their study of how audit quality affects the prices of shares of oil and gas companies quoted on the NSE found that audit quality enhances the market prices of shares of quoted oil and gas companies. Specifically, the study found that while auditor type, auditor independence and audit committee composition significantly affected share prices, auditor tenure did not.

Chinedu, Nwoha and Udeh, (2019) and Iliemena & Okolocha (2019) both used ROA to measure performance of listed manufacturing companies and listed industrial firms in Nigeria while adopting auditor independence, firm rotation, audit committee composition and audit fees as proxies for audit quality. However, while Chinedu, Nwoha & Udeh, (2019) found that auditor independence and audit committee composition significantly affect firm performance and audit fees did not, Iliemena & Okolocha (2019) found that audit fees actually affected performance of industrial firms in Nigeria.

Notwithstanding the fact that some researchers excluded financial firms when studying the effect of audit quality on firm performance, others exclusively used financial firms for their study. Thus, Tyokoso, U-ungwa &

Ojonimi (2017) used Tobin’s Q to measure performance of DMBs in Nigeria. Proxies found to positively measure performance of DMBs are auditor tenure and client importance while firm size and specialization of the auditor were not found to significantly affect performance.

Ogbodo and Akabuogu, (2018) and Ugwu, Aikpitanyi & Idemudia (2020) carried out an assessment of the effect of audit quality on the financial performance of banks in Nigeria using return on assets; return on equity and profitability margin as measures of performance. Both researchers found that firm size has significant effect on return on assets. Additionally, Ugwu, Aikpitanyi & Idemudia (2020) found that audit fees and joint audit negatively affect performance.

3. Methodology

The study adopted correlation and ex-post factor research design methodology by using pooled multiple regressions of panel data assessing the effect of audit quality on performance of DMBs in Nigeria.

3.1 Population and Sample

For the purpose of this study, the population comprises all the 16 DMBs listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) market as at 31st December, 2020. Banks that have complete data within the period of the study were included in the sample of the study while banks with inadequate data were excluded. With this sampling process, nine banks representing 56% of the population were selected as sample for the study. Data were sourced from the annual reports and financial statements of the sampled banks between 2012 and 2020. Year 2012 was selected as the base year because that was the year Nigeria DMBs were directed to start preparing financial statements in line with the provisions of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and year 2020 was chosen due to data availability.

3.2 Description of the Variables.

The dependent variables of this study were represented by two measures of performance viz: accounting and market measures. The accounting measure is proxied by return on assets (ROA) while the market measure of performance is represented by Tobin’s Q. The independent variable was represented by audit quality and measured by audit fees and auditor size while the two control variables are firm size and audit committee independence.

Data were sourced from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled DMBs while market price data were obtained from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) daily activity summary (equities) published in national

Table 1: Operation table

newspapers and the website of Cashcraft Assets Management Limited. The study used December month end closing prices for each period. The variables are operationalized as follows:

S/N	Variable	Description	Type	Measurements	Ref.	Expected Sign
1	ROA (accounting measure of performance)	Return on Assets	Dependent	Net Income/ Total Assets	Kumar, (2004); Horváthová,(2012)	+

2	Q(market measure of performance)	Tobin's Q	Dependent	Market value/ Total assets	Tyokoso, U-ungwa&Ojonimi (2017), Monametsi&Agasha (2020)	+
3	BIG 4	Auditor Size	Independent	Dichotomous variable 1 for Big4 auditors and 0 otherwise	Inaam, Khmoussi, & Fatma, (2012)	+
4	Fee	Audit Fees	Independent	Natural log of all fees paid to auditors	Zunaidah, et al. (2013), Hassan & Farouk, 2014	+
5	Size	Firm size	Control	Natural log of Total Assets	Monametsi & Agasha (2020).	+
6	Ind	Audit Committee Independence	Control	Number of Non-Executive Directors in Audit Committee		+

Source: Authors' compilation, 2021

3.3 Model Specification

Two models were used in this study and each of the models measure each of the dependent variables.

$$\text{Model I: } ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Fee} + \beta_2 \text{BIG4} + \beta_3 \text{Size} + \beta_4 \text{Ind} + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

$$\text{Model II: } Q = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Fee} + \beta_2 \text{BIG4} + \beta_3 \text{Size} + \beta_4 \text{Ind} + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots\dots\dots(ii) \text{ Where:}$$

ROA = Return on Asset (accounting measure of performance)

Q = Tobin's Q (market measure of performance)

Fee = Audit Fees

BIG4 = Big 4 accounting firms (Auditor size)

Size = Firm Size

Ind = Audit committee independence ε_t = Error term.

4 Analysis

4.1 Realization of Objective 1:

What effect does audit quality has on return on assets of DMBs in Nigeria

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Audit fees do not have any significant effect on ROA of Nigeria's DMBs. **H₁₁:** Audit fees have significant effect on ROA of Nigeria's DMBs.

Hypothesis 2

	BIG 4	.	.	1.000	.	.
	Firm size	.579	.583	.	1.000	.178
	Audit committee independence	.210	.094	.	.178	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	ROA	.	.002	.000	.000	.049
	Audit Fee	.002	.	.000	.000	.233
	BIG 4	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	Firm size	.000	.000	.000	.	.081
	Audit committee independence	.049	.233	.000	.081	.

H₀₂: Auditor size does not significantly affect ROA of Nigeria’s DMBs. **H₁₂:** Auditor size does significantly affect ROA of Nigeria’s DMBs.

Table 2: Correlation table, Audit quality vs accounting measure of performance

Correlations						
		ROA	Auditor Fee	BIG 4	Firm size	Audit committee independence
Pearson Correlation	ROA	1.000	.356	.	.579	.210
	Audit Fee	.356	1.000	.	.583	.094

Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 2.1, 202. 1

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.590 ^a	.348	.315	.0119702

a. Predictors: (Constant), Audit committee independence, Auditor Fee, Firm size Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 21, 2021.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.005	3	.002	10.503	.000 ^b
1 Residual	.008	59	.000		
Total	.013	62			

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

b. Predictors: (Constant), Audit committee independence, Auditor Fee, Firm size Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 21, 2021.

Table 5: Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.160	.041		-3.901	.000

Audit Fee	.002	.002	.029	.223	.824
Firm size	.010	.002	.543	4.146	.000
Audit committee independence	.021	.020	.111	1.039	.303
a. Dependent Variable: ROA					

Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 21, 2021.

Table 2 depicts that audit fees and auditor size have Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria (Table 5). Also, the positive coefficients of (0.356) and (0.579) with p-values: coefficients of the control variables such as Firm size and (0.002) and (0.000) respectively. This implies that audit Audit committee independence of 0.010 (0.000) and fees and auditor size have positive and significant 0.021 (0.303) respectively indicate that firm size has relations with return on asset (ROA). Positive and significant effect but audit committee the coefficient of determination R² is found to be high independence has insignificant relationship with DMBs’ 0.995473 or 99.6%, (table 3) meaning that over 99.6% of performance (measured with ROA).

The variations in the dependent variable (ROA) is 4.2 **Realization of Objective 2** explained by the observed explanatory variables in the How does audit quality affect the market value (Tobin’s model. This perhaps suggests that some of the variables Q) of Nigeria’s DMBs omitted from the regression may have been of no significance and is an indication of fitness of the model.

Hypothesis 3

The F-Statistic (table 4), in this model, has been **H03**: Audit fees do not have any significant effect on calculated as 10.503 and its corresponding p-value is just Tobin’s Q of Nigeria’s DMBs.

0.000. This also implies that we can reject the null **H13**: Audit fees do have significant effect on Tobin’s hypothesis of all slope coefficients being simultaneously Q of Nigeria’s DMBs.

Zero and thus assert that at least one of the explanatory **variables** has a significant effect on the dependent **Hypothesis 4** variable. Conversely, audit fees (p-value= 0.824) **H04**: Auditor size does not significantly affect Tobin’s unilaterally has no significant effect on ROA while Q of Nigeria’s DMBs.

Auditor size proxied as Big 4 (presence) is constant all **H14**: Auditor size significantly affects Tobin’s Q of through the observed banks with p-value = 0.000 which Nigeria’s DMBs. implies that auditor size has significant effect on ROA of

Table 6: Correlation table of Audit quality vs Market performance

Correlations						
		Q	Auditor Fee	BIG 4	Firm size	Audit committee independence
Pearson Correlation	Q	1.000	.091	.	.241	.135
	Audit Fee	.091	1.000	.	.583	.094
	BIG 4	.	.	1.000	.	.
	Firm size	.241	.583	.	1.000	.178
	Audit committee independence	.135	.094	.	.178	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	Q	.	.238	.000	.028	.145
	Audit Fee	.238	.	.000	.000	.233
	BIG 4	.000	.000	.	.000	.000

Firm size	.028	.000	.000	.081
Audit committee independence	.145	.233	.000	.081

Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 21, 2021.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.266 ^a	.071	.023	.0898012

a. Predictors: (Constant), Audit committee independence, Auditor Fee, Firm size Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 21, 2021.

Table 8: ANOVA^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.446	.307		-1.452	.152
1 Firm size	-.006	.013	-.073	-.475	.637
Audit independence	.029	.017	.267	1.709	.093
committee	.111	.149	.095	.742	.461

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.036	3	.012	1.494	.225 ^b
1 Residual	.476	59	.008		
Total	.512	62			

a. Dependent Variable: Q

b. Predictors: (Constant), Big 4, Audit committee independence, Auditor Fee, Firm size Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs. 21, 2021.

Table 9: Coefficients

a. Dependent Variable: Q

Source: Authors’ computation via SPSS vs 21, 2021.

Table 6 depicts that audit fee has positive but insignificant and weak relationship (0.091, p-value = 0.238) and auditor size has no relationship (0.000, p-value =0.000) which indicate total independent from market performance (Tobin’Q).

R² is found to be very low 0.071 or 7.1%, (table 7). This perhaps suggests that variations in dependent variable are explained by only 7.1% of the observed explanatory variables, meaning that some of the variables omitted from the regression may have been of significance. The F-Statistics of 1.494 with p-value = 0.225(table 8), means that we can accept the null hypothesis that states that none of the explanatory variables has a significant effect on the dependent variable of the study. Audit fees (pvalue= 0.637) has no significant effect on Tobin’Q while auditor

size proxied as Big 4 (presence) is constant all through the observed deposit money banks in Nigeria (Table 9). Also, both control variables (Firm size and Audit committee independence) asserts insignificant relationship with market performance (Tobin'Q) of DMBs in Nigeria.

5 Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study analyzed above actually confirm the inconclusiveness of research findings on audit quality and financial performance of firms.

This study showed that the big 4 audit firms employed by the banks assist in enhancing the performance of the banks since auditor size has a positive and significant effect on performance measured by ROA. This finding which is line with the postulates of the agency theory and it is also supported by findings of other researchers such as Hassan & Farouk (2014), Ogbodo and Akabuogu, (2018), Ado, et al, (2020) and Ugwu, et al, (2020). However, it contradicts the findings of Elewa & ElHaddad (2019) who posit that auditor size has no effect on performance of non-financial firms.

On the other hand, audit fees displayed an insignificant but positive relationship with bank's performance which is in contradiction of the a priori expectation of the study. This is very unfortunate since it probably means that the auditors looked the other way after collecting fantastic remuneration from the directors thus compromising their independence. Other researchers that have obtained similar result include Sayyar, et al (2015), Chinedu, et al (2019) and Monametsi & Agasha (2020). Findings of this study equally showed that none of the explanatory variables significantly affect market measure of performance. This means that none of the proxies of audit quality actually has effect on the performance of the banks a result which is at variance with agency theory upon which this study is based. Other researchers with similar findings include Santos, et al (2015), Tyokoso, et.al(2017), However, Okolie and Izedonmi (2014) maintained that audit firm size significantly influence market value of performance of listed firms in Nigeria.

6 Conclusion

The major banks failures which occurred in Nigeria have raised fears about the reliability of the financial reporting practices by listed banks in Nigeria. This agitated a number of regulatory and professional institutions to advocate for reforms that will enhance transparency in financial reporting and thus increase performance as well as audit quality. Therefore, this study offers proof on the direct influence of audit quality on the financial performance of listed banks using two performance measures (vis. market and accounting measures). This study employs multiple regression to examine the model. The results revealed that audit fee shows a positive and significant relationship with accounting performance (ROA) of DMBs. This implies that if there is decrease in the amount paid to auditors for audit services, then financial performance of listed deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria will not decrease. Consistent with the agency theory, auditor size displays a significant positive relationship with ROA. This positive figure implies that a percentage increase in firms audited by Big4, then financial performance (ROA) will also increase. Conversely, the audit fees and size have no significant effect on market measure of performance (Tobin'Q), though the relationships are positive but not significant.

7 Recommendations

The study recommends that: efforts should be made in creating environment that would improve the sustainability of audit quality not only in listed deposit money banks but be extended to private companies for enthrone of good corporate governance practices; The quality of audit should be maintained and improved upon by keeping audit objectives such as: financial control mechanisms, implementation of acts, rules and regulation; The study

also recommends that the executives should engage the services provided by audit firms whose integrity and character is unquestionable. It will also assist policy makers and relevant authorities in decision making.

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